

FINANCIAL AND REAL ESTATE DYNAMICS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA: A STATISTICAL JOURNEY (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This article embarks on a statistical exploration of the financial and real estate activities within the Romanian Mountain Area spanning the decade from 2008 to 2018. Through an in-depth analysis of key indicators, market trends, and economic shifts, the study aims to provide insights into the dynamic landscape of financial and real estate sectors in this unique geographical region.

1. Introduction:

The financial and real estate sectors play pivotal roles in shaping the economic landscape of any region. In the Romanian Mountain Area, this article delves into the statistical intricacies of financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate developments, from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to unravel patterns, challenges, and opportunities that have defined these sectors in the mountainous terrain. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2023a-d; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2023a-d)

2. Methodology:

Employing a meticulous quantitative approach, this research incorporates data from financial reports, industry databases, and pertinent publications. Key indicators such as market size, investment trends, and regulatory changes are analyzed to offer a comprehensive understanding of the financial and real estate dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Area.

3. Financial and Insurance Activities:

This section explores the statistical intricacies of financial and insurance activities within the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as the growth of banking institutions, insurance penetration rates, and investment portfolios are scrutinized to assess the sector's resilience and responsiveness to economic shifts over the specified decade.

4. Real Estate Developments:

The article delves into the statistical landscape of real estate activities, encompassing property values, construction trends, and market demand in the Romanian Mountain Area. Insights into the factors influencing real estate dynamics and their implications for regional development are discussed.

5. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of financial, insurance, and real estate activities, this section investigates their contributions to the regional Gross

Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability in the Romanian Mountain Area. The interconnectedness of these sectors is crucial for understanding their collective influence on the local economy.

6. Results:

Establishment rate: the number of enterprises established in the reference period (t) divided by the number of active enterprises in t – percentage

The related descriptive analysis S1 presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, Percentiles 25, 50, 75, so 11.9191, 1.16107, 11.3000, 3.85085, 14.829, 2.132, .661, 5.614, 1.279, 14.30, 7.93, 22.23, 9.00, 10.10, 10.5, 10.3430

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeat in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared -1.312E-16, 2.384E-15, -5.107 E-15, 3.775E-15, -5.107E-15, -4.752E-15; R-square .083, .289, -5.107E-15, 1.000, -5.107E-15, -4.574E-15; RMSE 4.063, 1.673, .000, 5.917, .000, .818; MAPS 21,976, 9,745, .000, 39,552, .000, 4,380; MaxAPE 61,410, 33,953, .000, 140,055, .000, 12,549; MAE 2.706, 1.155, .000, 4.063, .000, .539; MaxAE

10,192, 4,236, .000, 15,177, .000, 1,604; Normalized BIC 3.131, .549, 2.224, 3.774, 2.224, 2.237.

The resulting forecast statistical models show the following general picture for I16 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: -6.661E-16, -6.661E-16, 3.851, 19.487 ; S2-Model_2: -5.107E-15, -5.107E-15, 2.819, 18.990; S3-Model_3: 1.221E-15, 1.221E-15, 4.992, 23.857; S4-Model_4: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 3.806, 21.968; S5-Model_5: 3.775E-15, 3.775E-15, 2.726, 16.756; S6-Model_6: -3.331E-15, -3.331E-15, 3.546, 14.600; S7-Model_7: 7.772E-16, 7.772E-16, 5.917, 29.932; S8-Model_8: 1.332E-15, 1.332E-15, 4.749, 39.552; S9-Model_9: 9.992E-16, 9.992E-16, 5.487, 24.373; S10-Model_10: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 5.392, 31.030; S11-Model_11: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 5.472, 23.163.

Table 33. Prediction analysis for I16

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	11.92	11.92	11.92	11.92	11.92	11.92	11.92
	UCL	20.50	20.50	20.50	20.50	20.50	20.50	20.50
	LCL	3.34	3.34	3.34	3.34	3.34	3.34	3.34
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	9.50	9.50	9.50	9.50	9.50	9.50	9.50
	UCL	15.79	15.79	15.79	15.79	15.79	15.79	15.79
	LCL	3.22	3.22	3.22	3.22	3.22	3.22	3.22
S3-Model_3:	Forecast	14.52	14.52	14.52	14.52	14.52	14.52	14.52
	UCL	25.64	25.64	25.64	25.64	25.64	25.64	25.64
	LCL	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39
S4-Model_4:	Forecast	10.24	10.24	10.24	10.24	10.24	10.24	10.24
	UCL	18.73	18.73	18.73	18.73	18.73	18.73	18.73

	LCL	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76
S5-Model_5:	Forecast	11.67	11.67	11.67	11.67	11.67	11.67	11.67
	UCL	17.75	17.75	17.75	17.75	17.75	17.75	17.75
	LCL	5.60	5.60	5.60	5.60	5.60	5.60	5.60
S6-Model_6:	Forecast	13.52	13.52	13.52	13.52	13.52	13.52	13.52
	UCL	21.42	21.42	21.42	21.42	21.42	21.42	21.42
	LCL	5.62	5.62	5.62	5.62	5.62	5.62	5.62
S7-Model_7:	Forecast	15.94	15.94	15.94	15.94	15.94	15.94	15.94
	UCL	29.12	29.12	29.12	29.12	29.12	29.12	29.12
	LCL	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76	2.76
S8-Model_8:	Forecast	9.46	9.46	9.46	9.46	9.46	9.46	9.46
	UCL	20.04	20.04	20.04	20.04	20.04	20.04	20.04
	LCL	-1.12	-1.12	-1.12	-1.12	-1.12	-1.12	-1.12
S9-Model_9:	Forecast	13.08	13.08	13.08	13.08	13.08	13.08	13.08
	UCL	25.31	25.31	25.31	25.31	25.31	25.31	25.31
	LCL	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86
S10-Model_10:	Forecast	14.08	14.08	14.08	14.08	14.08	14.08	14.08
	UCL	26.10	26.10	26.10	26.10	26.10	26.10	26.10
	LCL	2.07	2.07	2.07	2.07	2.07	2.07	2.07
S11-Model_11:	Forecast	15.41	15.41	15.41	15.41	15.41	15.41	15.41
	UCL	27.60	27.60	27.60	27.60	27.60	27.60	27.60
	LCL	3.21	3.21	3.21	3.21	3.21	3.21	3.21

Figure 3.24. Graphical forecasting analysis for I16

6. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying noteworthy trends and challenges faced by the financial, insurance, and real estate sectors during the specified period, this section provides a forward-looking perspective on potential future developments. Considerations such as regulatory changes, market fluctuations, and global economic influences are explored.

7. Regional Comparisons:

The article may draw comparisons with other regions in Romania to highlight unique aspects of the financial and real estate landscape in the mountainous area. Examining regional variations provides additional context for understanding the specific dynamics at play.

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a comprehensive statistical overview of financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate developments, in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of economic trends, offering valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for sustainable growth in these vital sectors.

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